

RESILIENCE

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

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List of Abbreviations

Abbr	Meaning
BoD	Board of Directors
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator(s)
M	Month
PPP	Preparatory Phase Project
RI	Research Infrastructure
TM	Team Member(s)
TNA	Transnational Access
WP	Work Package
WU	Working Unit

List of Partner Acronyms

Abbr	Meaning
FSCIRE	FSCIRE (Coordinator)
BIU	Bar Ilan University
CINECA	CINECA
EPHE	École Pratique des Hautes Études
INFAI	InfAI
KUL	KU Leuven
TUA	Theological University of Apeldoorn
UFO	Albanian University
UNISOFIA	Sofia University
UNSA	University of Sarajevo
UNIWARSAW	University of Warsaw

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VOLOS Volos Academy for Theological Studies
WWU University of Münster

1 Introduction

In the RESILIENCE PPP Grant Agreement,¹ the primary objective for WP4 reads: “Updating and implementing the Communication & Dissemination Plan during the Preparatory Phase and to develop a communication study dedicated to the specificity and typology of services and datasets for religious studies.” For the latter part of the objective, reference may be made to Deliverable D4.4.

The present deliverable builds on the first version of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, Deliverable D4.1 which was published November, 2022.

In D4.2, we present the main principles for communication and dissemination, then we describe the updates of our three communication strategies. Statistics especially show what, how, when and to whom communicated.

How we worked on the objective is further elaborated in some focal points and specific tasks, which are reviewed in Chapter 4. Besides, this chapter reports on the updates based upon reviewers advice and upon insights collected by the WU CDE team in the previous period and progress made by the consortium.

New in this deliverable, as compared to the previous deliverable D4.1, is the exploitation chapter, describing a first version of the terms for exploitation as well as its strategy.

In the subsequent chapters the reader will understand how the Communication /Dissemination/Exploitation (CDE) Team worked up to this point and what results are already on the horizon. However, not all information is part of this public deliverable. The information in the Appendix is intended for intern use and for reporting to the European Commission and therefore not visible through this public deliverable.

At the moment of writing this deliverable and from the results as presented in the annex it can be concluded that concerning communication and dissemination we are building momentum: we are on the way to achieving our goals and handling various tasks. What has not been completed (yet or not enough yet) will be described in the last version of the plan, Deliverable D4.3, which will be published January, 2026.

¹ GA 101079792, Description of Action, Part A, 9.

2 Key Principles for Communication and Dissemination

2.1 Assumptions

The Key Principles for Communication and Dissemination can be found in the strategic plan D4.1. The following assumptions described in D4.1 have remained in full force for D4.2:

- An agile approach, resulting in an agile communication strategy (the three communication strategy frames).
- A communication strategy focusing on Europe.
- In the cycle of communication, both WU CDE and the consortium partners are multipliers, namely of each other's news, and initiators in the sense of supplying news and other things to be announced.
- Geographical preconditions: each partner is responsible for communication/dissemination in one or more European countries according to the previously defined geographical distribution.²

Figure 1 Cycle of communication and Actors

² RESILIENCE Deliverable D4.1, 14-15.

2.2 Communication and Dissemination

Given that there is a difference between communication³ and dissemination,⁴ and also that RESILIENCE is in the Preparatory Phase with few concrete results to be taken up yet by its users, there is no difference between communication and dissemination in this plan in terms of approach, with one exception: the Transnational Access (TNA) Fellowship Programme. This program is up and running and is being used by scholars from all over Europe. The strategy for TNA is housed in a separate communication strategy frame, while results are collected separately under the Dissemination heading.

2.3 Goals

The General Strategic Goals for RESILIENCE's communication and dissemination are:

- Raising awareness about RESILIENCE.
- Influencing target audiences in their perception of RESILIENCE (their perception develops into a growing awareness of the need of an RI for the study of religion, as well as knowing how to make use of it).

These General Strategic Goals are further defined in specific strategic goals for both internal and external communication:

Specific Strategic Goals for Internal Communication:

- Supporting partners find their role in the communication and dissemination activities.
- Achieving the highest level of participation by all partners in the communication and dissemination activities.

Specific Strategic Goals for External Communication:

- Spreading information about the RI.
- Attracting target audiences, so that they can play an active part in the Preparatory Phase and thereafter.

³ Communication is a strategically planned process of transmission of information, aimed at promoting the action and its results to multiple audiences, including media and the public.

⁴ Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means - this includes scientific publications in any medium - with the aim to enable others to use and take up results.

2.4 Target Audiences

RESILIENCE's target audiences have been defined as follows, whereas two additions were made, the civil society and new partners from other countries:

ACADEMIC

- Professors.
- Experts.
- Scholars and students.
- Research and/or educational institutions.
- Members of RIs and other research networks in Europe.⁵
- Libraries.

NON-ACADEMIC

- Professionals in religious communities or churches.
- NGOs.
- Civil Society⁶

NEW PARTNERS

- GLAM-Institutions (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums).
- Potential business investors (to be defined in a later stage).
- New partners from other countries.⁷

DECISION MAKERS

- Governmental institutions or organisations.
- Policy makers.

MEDIA

⁵ RESILIENCE is interested in entering into a proactive relationship with other European projects and RIs related in the field, because it expects to benefit from them and it expects that there will be a mutual benefit (synergy). Other European projects and RIs are, for example, CLARIN and DARIAH. Because of the aim of a relationship, it is most effective to start with connections on a management level (directors connect with directors), the level where the decisions are made. Starting 2019, the following contacts have been made: CLARIN ERIC, CLARIN IT, CLARIAH, DARIAH ERIC, CESSDA ERIC, EHRI, IPERION, EOSC, SSHOC, E-RIHS, H2IOSC, Time Machine Organisation, EUROPEANA, and EATRIS ERIC, Euro-Bioluming ERIC, eRImote, Skills4EOSC, VEREAD, Science Europe, Eastern Christian Studies - Online Campus, University Research Priority Program (URPP) 'Digital Religions', University of Zürich.

⁶ Additional target audiences were added, based on reviewer's advice, December 2023.

⁷ The General Assembly of RESILIENCE appointed an Enlargement Committee, which is addressing this target group.

- Television and radio.
- Newspapers.
- Online media.
- Self-owned media channels.
- Journalists.

2.5 General Messages

The general messages as formulated in D4.1 were in need of an update. This was because of the progress of the work of the other WPs and because of the publication of a new vision/mission statement. In addition, derived messages were defined in the general partner matrix and the specific partner matrices.

To arrive at a core message and a clear set of sub-messages from the vision/mission document, grounded in the services we will offer, the Message House model was used.⁸ In keeping with WP3 Services' choice of three archetypes (Researchers, Librarians and Archivists), the Message House is filled out for these audiences. All other messages for different target groups are defined in the generic partner matrix, the messages in the partner matrices (see Appendix) can be further tailored towards different target audiences and contexts using the Golden Circle (par. 2.7).

⁸ The tool of the Message House describes the core message, arguments and supporting facts. It helps to keep the communication consistent and coherent.

Figure 2 Message House for Academics

Figure 3 Message House for Librarians/Archivists

2.6 Tools, Channels and Touchpoints

For internal and external communication, a number of tools, channels and touchpoints have been developed. They are constantly under review, to enable updates.⁹

Tools and Channels for Internal Communication are: E-mail, email lists, email signature, project management tool (ClickUp), video conference, online project repository, guides, face to face meetings, communication toolkit, content calendar.

The touchpoints for External Communication are: Website, newsletter, social media channels, keywords, PPT template, stationary, word templates, excel template, press release format, press contact list, business cards, posters and flyers, banner, noteblock, videos, hashtags, YouTube, face to face contacts, personal contacts. After the publication of D4.1, the following additional touchpoints were included in the list: Panels at the annual conference of the European Academy of Religion and traditional media (newspapers etc.).

2.7 Sinek's Golden Circle Model

In order to be able to present RESILIENCE as a brand and to convince our audiences of the necessity of a RI for the study of religion, the choice was made to use the Golden Circle model, developed by Simon Sinek, differentiating the value proposition. The value proposition specifies what makes one's services attractive to users or clients, why they should make use of them and how the value of the product or service is differentiated from similar offerings. To define the value proposition and to convey the message convincingly we practiced the method of The Golden Circle during in-person training in Mg.

The Golden Circle contains three circles with each one asking an important question: the Why?, the How? and the What? Following Sinek, it is important to start with the core WHY question and not with the WHAT.

The **WHY** is about what an organization believes in, the reason for its existence.

The **HOW** is an explanation of what the organization does.

The **WHAT** represents the products or services a company or organization offers/sells.

⁹ See for further definition of the tools, channels and touchpoints Deliverable D4.1, p. 80-98.

Figure 4 Sinek's Golden Circle Model

This method assumes that presenters are able to adapt their message to their audience and have sufficient knowledge of the RI's developments. The values formulated in the vision/mission document can help in this respect.¹⁰

The model also supports presenters in tailoring messages to different target groups, including the civil society and the private sector, thus ensuring a more effective connection to these groups.

For the communication plan, this means that except for the specific messages in the partner matrix, derived from the general messages, no further differentiation by religious, social or cultural context has been made, but that this is left to the individual presenter.

2.8 Generic Partner Matrice

For D4.1 and previous CDP's for RESILIENCE's Design Phase, and based on the partner matrices developed by the partners themselves, a generic partner matrix was established. This generic partner matrix is meant to support WP4 and the partners in their communication and dissemination activities, because via the matrix

¹⁰ The vision/mission statement is online accessible via <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/we-are-resilience/vision-and-mission/>

they get a quick overview of the target audiences, their needs, the core messages, the tools, channels and touchpoints to be used and specific goals to be achieved.

Each partner communicates in English as its main language and decides per communication or dissemination activity whether it is necessary to communicate in the native language of their target audience as well. For some partners in the Eastern European and Balkan areas, the native language of the target audiences sometimes differs from their own native language.

Each target audience is served via a specified number of tools, channels and touchpoints, derived from the overview in D4.1¹¹ and as summarized in Chapter 2.6 of this document, whereby 11 and 12 have been added to the original list. In the generic partner matrix below, you can find the numbers of the tools, channels or touchpoints that are used per audience. The numbers relate to:

1. Website.
2. Newsletter.
3. Flyers/posters.
4. Press Releases.
5. Videos.
6. Social Media channels (partners choose their own preferred channels, such as Facebook, X (Twitter) or Instagram).
7. Face to face collaboration (this applies only to the Preparatory Phase, and divides into different categories, as explained in par. 10.10).
8. Conferences/workshops.
9. Self-owned Media channels.
10. Personnel contacts.
11. Panels at the annual conference of the European Academy of Religion.
12. Traditional media (newspapers).

Each partner is responsible for how frequently they communicate, and chooses its own preferred tools, channels or touchpoints.

Based on the overview of target audiences (par. 2.4) and the tools, channels and touchpoints listed above, a generic partner matrix has been developed as a template for the more specific partner matrices in the Appendix. To serve the target audience best, their interests and needs as well as specific core messages have been added to the generic partner matrix. The core messages have been derived from the general messages and adapted with the interests and needs of the target audiences in mind.

¹¹ See for further definition of the tools, channels and touchpoints Deliverable D4.1, p. 80-98.

Target Audience	Interest/Need	Core Message	Tools, Channels and Touchpoints
Category: Academic			
Professors	They want facilitated access to scientific resources, they want to expand their community and their international network and they want to offer expert assistance in solving ongoing political and religious issues.	RESILIENCE offers you a unique gateway to resources and services for the study of religion.	1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
Experts	They want facilitated access to scientific resources, they want to expand their community, to expand their international network and they want to offer expert assistance in solving ongoing political and religious issues.	RESILIENCE offers you a unique gateway to resources related to the study of religion.	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
Scholars and students	They want to develop their career, exchange new ideas, get publicity for their research output, enter the academic network and expand their academic contacts.	RESILIENCE boosts your academic career and creates new opportunities for knowledge exchange and networking.	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Research and/or educational institutions	They want facilitated access to scientific resources, to expand their community and gain international contacts. They are able to share their own data and output.	RESILIENCE makes research easier, and increases your visibility.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
Members of other RI and research networks in Europe	They want to make use of the expertise of other institutions and they want to cooperate to create synergy. They want to expand their network with new researchers or RIs.	RESILIENCE is open to cooperation and offers its expertise to you.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11
Libraries	They want to serve their users with the latest data and data tools. They want to make their holdings accessible and more visible to others and be up-to-date with new developmental instruments and/or products.	RESILIENCE helps you to optimize the service to your users and makes others aware of your resources.	1, 2, 6, 7
Category: Non-academic			
Professionals in religious communities or churches	Facing the challenges of a multi-religious society, they want easy access to knowledge and to experts in the field.	RESILIENCE offers you a unique access to scientific-based knowledge and to	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11

		experts in the field of the study of religion.	
NGO-organisations with a similar field (e.g. humanitarian or religious organisations)	They need visibility, knowledge and a platform for their message. They want affordable use of the newest tools and techniques related to collections.	RESILIENCE helps you to be seen and heard, and to find relevant information and to get training on the newest tools.	4, 6, 10
Civil Society	Facing the challenges of a multi-religious society, they want to know what answers can be given.	RESILIENCE shares with you science-based information and expertise to deal with religion.	6, 12
Category: New Partners			
GLAM-institutions	They want affordable use of the newest tools and techniques related to collections. They want to enlarge the audience for their collections, optimize storage.	RESILIENCE helps you to strengthen your specific and essential role in research.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 10
Potential business investors	They want to make money and a good impression and see an opportunity to do so via RESILIENCE.	RESILIENCE opens up new markets for you.	1, 2, 6, 10
New partners from countries where partners are located, or on which their communication activities focus, see also chapter 10.3.	They constantly look for ways to better reach their goals, such as: facilitated access to scientific resources or expanding their community and/or their international network.	If your goals relate to the study of religion, RESILIENCE is the right infrastructure for you.	1, 2, 3, 6, 10
Category: Decision Makers			
Governmental institutions or organisations	They need easy access to the achievements of country-specific and international researchers in the study of religion and want to boost their international cooperation on the topic.	RESILIENCE offers you shares with you science-based information, data and expertise to deal with religions.	1, 2, 4, 6, 10
Policy makers	They need information and expertise on topics related to the study of religion.	RESILIENCE gives access to a wide range of information and expertise on religions.	1, 2, 4, 6, 10
Category: Media			
Television and radio	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who can reflect and inform on current issues.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10

Newspapers	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who can reflect and inform on current issues.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10
Online media	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who can reflect and inform on current issues.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10
Self-owned media channels	They need input related to the study of religion and ways to promote their institution.	RESILIENCE offers you ideas, topics, themes and a podium to present your institution and contents.	4, 10
Journalists	They need easy access to information and to experts in the field of religion. They want to gather and communicate news on issues related to religion.	RESILIENCE offers you easy access to information and to a wide pool of experts, who can reflect and inform on current issues.	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10

Table 1 Generic Partner Matrix

2.9 Specific Goals per Target Audience

For each target audience in the above matrix we now formulate specific goals, as a tool to measure progress. We have answered three questions, based on the KAB-model: Knowledge, Attitude, Behaviour. This model focuses on measuring behavioral change (Schrader & Lawless, 2004). Each question is answered for one or more target audience, as you can see in Table 2.

1. Knowledge: what should they know about RESILIENCE?

1. They know what RESILIENCE can do for them and how they can contribute to the RI (in the future).
2. They know how to benefit from the services that RESILIENCE is offering.
3. They know how to benefit from RESILIENCE and how to contribute (in the future).
4. They know that RESILIENCE offers tools and services for an innovative approach to the study of religion, which can be used to build a European response to the challenge of religious diversity.

2. Attitude: what should their attitude towards RESILIENCE look like?

1. They are convinced of the usefulness of the infrastructure (in the future).
2. They should see RESILIENCE as an obvious RI to find tools for an innovative approach to the study of religion which can be used to build a European response to the challenge of religious diversity.
3. They are willing to contribute to and use the infrastructure.

3. Behaviour: what should they do with RESILIENCE or how should they engage with it?

1. They should start using the services of RESILIENCE and/or act as a contributor.
2. They should spread the knowledge of RESILIENCE by acting as an ambassador.
3. They should spread news from and about RESILIENCE.

Target audience	Knowledge	Attitude	Behaviour
Category: Academic			
Professors	1.1	2.1	3.1
Experts	1.1	2.1	3.1
Scholars and students	1.1	2.1	3.1
Research and/or educational institutions	1.1	2.1	3.1
Members of other RI and research networks in Europe	1.1	2.1	3.1
Libraries	1.1	2.1	3.1
Category: Non-academic			
Professionals in religious community or churches	1.2	2.2	3.1
NGO-organisations with a similar field (e.g. humanitarian or religious organisations)	1.2	2.2	3.2
Civil Society	1.4	2.1	3.1
Category: New Partners			
GLAM-institutions	1.2	2.2	3.1
Potential business investors	1.2	2.3	3.1
New partners from other countries	1.2	2.3	3.1

Table 2 Specific Goals per Target Audience

3 Communication Strategy

The Communication Strategy Frame has been taken as a guide for an agile development of the communication strategy. RESILIENCE's communication strategy is defined in three frames¹²:

- A general Communication Strategy Frame.
- A Communication Strategy Frame for Eastern Europe and the Balkans.
- A Communication Strategy Frame for TNA.

¹² Based on B. van Ruler (2021), *Handboek communicatiestrategie. Agile methode voor strategie-ontwikkeling*, Amsterdam: Boom Uitgevers.

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The three frames were completed and established based on a set of guiding questions in each of the eight blocks, indicating the internal and external situation, the stakeholders and resources and the key elements of vision, ambition, accountability and gameplan.

Figure 5 Communication Strategy Frame Template

The first version of the frames was published in D4.1 of RESILIENCE's Design Phase. However, a strategy is never finished and therefore needs regular updating. The WU CDE TM were able to update the three frames in December 2023, including an updated set of KPIs for the project period.

3.1 General Communication Strategy Frame

The main updates included in version 02.00¹³ are:

- Ambitions are formulated for the end of this phase (in 2026).
- Ambitions internal communication deleted, since they are achieved.
- Some general simplifications or summaries.
- The draft service catalogue and the vision/mission statement were added to the resources.

The main updates included in version 03.00 are:

- Alignment with the vision/mission statement.
- Additional stakeholder group: civil society.
- Increasing clarity about the services offered (based on D2.2).

¹³ This 02.00 version is considered as a working version, since it is not included in a deliverable.

Internal Situation

- Increasing clarity about services that will be offered.
- A common compass defining the main elements and values for our work is available.
- The consortium works with a more defined vision/mission statement.
- RESILIENCE as the RI for the study of religion is moving towards full operation.

Vision

- RESILIENCE connects research centers, data holders and services distributed all over Europe and creates new instruments and services for its scientific community.
- RESILIENCE facilitates faster, better, and more efficient research, as well as access to online and physical sources. It offers a central place where to find evolving tools and big data.
- RESILIENCE enters the field of new developments of Open Science, offering FAIR access to data and storing data as well as to resources, tools, etc.
- Communication is integrated within the consortium and serves all WUs to reach their goals.

Accountability

- WU CDE uses the convincing narrative of the RI, (the updated vision/mission statement), sees to sufficient publicity. Other WUs will support this, and deliver content.
- TUA shares event feedback within the consortium.
- TUA organizes monitoring and reporting and supports partners in this respect.
- TUA supports the consortium in organizing workshops and events initiated by BOD.
- Partners redistribute news.
- Partners present RESILIENCE on events and in media, deliver content for website. TUA puts an emphasis on presentations.

Stakeholders

- Internal: WU CDE members.
- External: 8 archetypes as defined by WU Users.
- Target Audiences: Academics, Non-academics (Religious Community, NGO's, civil society), Decision makers, New partners, Media.

External Situation

- Depending on their context, stakeholders can be convinced of the necessity of a RI for Religious Studies.
- Our audiences are interested in services that are up and running.

Ambition

In 2026:

- RESILIENCE is recognized in Europe and beyond as a unique and indispensable RI.
- Target audiences are aware of the RI and of relevant developments within the WUs.
- Target audiences are convinced of the added value of RESILIENCE.

Gameplan

- Agile and goal-oriented approach: adapt to developments and progress made within the RI.
- Implement communication around available services (TNA/RelResearch)/relevant developments/events through existing channels, press releases and free publicity.
- Establish and execute the Action Plan.
- Organize feedback collection after events.
- Organize presentations (Push) on conferences and via personal contacts, emphasizing the added value of the RI.
- Draft more types of events showing the innovative and digital character of the RI.
- Organize collaborative WU CDE Meetings on a regular base.

Resources

- Efforts as in WBS. In descending order: TUA, Uni Sofia, UFO, UNSA, CINECA, WWU, Fscire, Volos, BIU, EPHE, InfAI, KU Leuven, Uni Warsaw.
- In-kind contributions (activities without any efforts in return).
- EU Grant.
- Knowledge on the upcoming services and their status.
- Ability to show the added value and the WHY of RESILIENCE to the stakeholders.
- Draft service catalogue and vision/mission statement.

3.2 Communication Strategy Frame for Eastern Europe and The Balkans

No less than five of the 13 RESILIENCE partners are located in **Eastern Europe and the Balkans**, namely UFO, UNISOFIA, UNSA, UNIWARSAW and VOLOS, which means that RESILIENCE has a special focus on these areas. With regards especially to the Balkans this is important because it reflects the less-known multi-religious and multicultural character of these areas along with the richness and historical value of their traditions, whose heritage still often remains inaccessible to the wider research community.

Partners in Eastern Europe and the Balkans will be faced with specific regional and/or cultural issues. UFO, UNSA, and VOLOS have their own strategy for reaching target audiences and for working on their ambitions. The slightly modified text compared to the strategies in D4.1 are below:

UFO's strategy shall focus on two colleges that teach the study of religion as part of their academic curriculum. One is focused on Islamic studies and the other mostly focuses on orthodox theology; both are founded and promoted with the support of each of their respective religious communities. AU will cooperate with them for the organization of an open-lecture and a presentation, and will use the research data and services of RESILIENCE for spreading knowledge. Invited in these activities will be participants from academic staff and students. The events will be posted in all social media accounts of the university for a better dissemination of RI activities.

Representation of the study of religion in academic institutions and relationship of the general audience in Albania with their respective beliefs is also a great source of academic information and for reaching potential partners in future academic activities. In this respect, AU will organize a meeting with heads of the Albanian Muslim Community, in order to include the sources of the Resilience Infrastructure at the venues of the newly-built Grand Mosque. Therefore, UFO will be able to reach not only the category of researchers among them, but also their followers.

To bring groups of interest closer to academic circles, UFO's plan is to expand its cooperation with different state structures that have access to or have contacts with researchers in the field of the study of religion, such as The State Committee of Cults, with which a collaboration has already started and will continue with promotion of the research infrastructure. An important partner will also be the General Directorate of Archives that will provide data on the study of religion, such as rare manuscripts important for the study of religion in Albania.

Within the UFO, RESILIENCE has been included in the annual plan of scientific and research activities, to be presented among the researchers, students, and partners. There are no specific studies in the study of religion at UFO and the Social Sciences Faculty is oriented in education, psychology, law and political and

administrative studies. The scholars and academics of all the social sciences are interested in the study of religion in general.

Regarding Kosovo and North Macedonia, scholars and researchers from these countries will be encouraged to become part of all activities and also, to organize common activities with UFO in the framework of RESILIENCE.

UNISOFIA will continue its efforts to cooperate with potential partners in Eastern and Central Europe in regard to RI development. Therefore, UNISOFIA will efficiently involve a growing group of academics who are engaged in the study of religion, and also students as well as young scholars to use the research data and services of RESILIENCE for producing new knowledge. The Bulgarian cultural environment provides a unique opportunity for involving the different religious communities (Orthodox, Catholics, Protestants, Muslims, Jews, Armenians, etc.) in our activities, which UNISOFIA considers as added value to the RESILIENCE Consortium. UNISOFIA will promote the Research infrastructure in this direction.

UNISOFIA will put emphasis on social media activities regarding the increase of Bulgarian followers of RESILIENCE social media channels. UNISOFIA will focus on organizing a few meetings (virtual, hybrid or physical) with local audiences – NGO's, experts, and community groups to promote the developing Research Infrastructure on the study of religion. Finally, UNISOFIA is discussing internally its regional activities according to the partner matrix, as well as making use of video production and other advertising materials being considered.

UNSA plans to focus again on physical events and get-togethers. International cooperation between the Faculty of Islamic Studies, Catholic Theological Faculty, Ghazi Husraw Bey's Library of UNSA and similar establishments in the region and beyond is significant. UNSA and its staff are very active both in receiving visitors from abroad and attending events internationally. The plan is to present RESILIENCE at these events whenever feasible. Under normal circumstances there should be at least ten such opportunities every year. An updated Fact Sheet printed locally and PowerPoint Presentation would be sufficient for that purpose.¹⁴

VOLOS continues its efforts to identify potential partners in the region of its responsibility and beyond based on its international networking (e.g. Baltic countries). Volos also aims at reaching a considerable amount of people mainly through the use of social media, regularly sent newsletters, presentations at events, and press releases which will further facilitate the networking of RESILIENCE in the regions under the Volos responsibility. In addition, it will make use of various local media (e.g. non-academic journals) to approach grassroots people in their respective mother-tongue. Finally it will function as a point of reference / as an entrance point for those from Eastern and Central Europe who would like to join the RI and use its

¹⁴ These means were offered to the partners.

services and network for research. For this purpose Pull communication tools like face to face collaboration, presentations, feedback collection, social media interaction, etc., will be used.

Argumentation for updated Strategy/KPIs for VOLOS in D4.2: With the experience of COVID-19 right behind us, webinars have been included in VOLOS's strategy. However, given the changing circumstances, the focus came to be centered on presenting RESILIENCE during physical events. Because of the higher emphasis on events, the delivery of blogs has been removed from the strategy and KPIs. The number of press releases has been brought down proportionally, as it was found that this is not a priority and VOLOS also depends on this from the press releases prepared by RESILIENCE.

In collaboration with UFO, UNISOFIA, UNSA, and VOLOS, the following updated version of the Communication Strategy Frame for Eastern Europe and the Balkans was developed. One of the main updates concerns the impression of the external situation, which seems to be improved. Was there first the belief that stakeholders are not always convinced of the necessity of a RI for the study of religion, the situation is now regarded such that, depending on the context, stakeholders can be convinced of the necessity of a RI for the study of religion. Besides, the estimate at this time is that audiences are interested in services that are up and running.

3.3 Communication Strategy Frame for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme

Considering the stage of development of the TNA service, as well as the good performance of previous coordinated efforts, it seemed desirable to start describing a specific communication strategy for the RESILIENCE TNA programme and associated workflow, to provide clarity within the consortium and towards the external audience. In establishing the frame and workflow for the programme, we drew on our own experiences as well as from insights from former ReIReS TNA grant holders, with whom RESILIENCE met and who provided valuable advice for improving communications around TNA. Tips that came in via email were also discussed and integrated where possible.

In collaboration with WU Services, a derivative of the overarching Communication Strategy Frame was created for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme, one of the services that is available right now.

A workflow accompanies the frame, specifying the specific actions for each RESILIENCE TNA fellowship both before, during and after this fellowship. This workflow is located as a guide in the Guide repository of WU CDE in the project G-Drive.

Internal situation

- The TNA programme is not a scholarship.
- The TNA programme is expanding by a growing number of hosts, experts, collections, etc.

Vision

- RESILIENCE offers in the TNA programme direct, fast, and effective access to collections, guided by experts.
- RESILIENCE offers TNA hosts a network of libraries, archives, institutes of higher education and other partners in Europe and makes their collections known to top researchers.
- Communication supports the TNA programme in making the programme known and facilitating matching scholars with institutions and institutions with RESILIENCE.

Accountability

- TUA is responsible for the overall coordination and implementation of the communication on the TNA programme.
- KU Leuven is responsible for delivering proper input for various means before, during, and after the call.
- TUA will monitor and report the results of the TNA communication.
- KU Leuven encourages external TNA hosts to be active in dissemination.
- Posts on TNA fellowship stays are made by TUA in collaboration with and according to preferences of these scholars.

KPIs 2023-2026

- Total number of new TNA hosts from outside the consortium at the end of the project: 15.
- Number of posts on social media related to TNA: 180.
- Number of TNA Fellowship Applications: 30.

Stakeholders

- Internal: TNA hosts/WU CDE (TUA and KU Leuven)/WU Research Services (KU Leuven)
- External: researchers, experts and (new) hosts
- Target Audiences: Academics and New partners

External situation

- Institutes are not aware of the possibilities and benefits being a TNA host.
- There is a growing awareness of the possibilities and benefits of the TNA programme, both among hosts and scholars.
- Scholars may not participate in the TNA Programme because there is no funding available.

Ambition

- Researchers and host institutions are aware of and react to dissemination concerning the RESILIENCE TNA programme.
- Researchers benefit from the dissemination possibilities of RESILIENCE (newsitems, interviews, reference to publications etc.).
- The network of TNA hosts has expanded with libraries, archives, and partners from outside the consortium

Gameplan

- Agile approach in communication: adapt the frame to developments and progress made.
- While communicating on the TNA Programme, the benefits will be emphasized.
- The focus will be on press releases, newsitems, newsletters, and social media.
- A workflow is available, indicating the tasks to do before, during, and after the call.
- In 2024 two call for applications for TNA fellowships are planned (Feb/March and Oct/Nov). There will be no call for hosting institutions.
- TUA discusses with TNA team if/how to include the GLAM sector in the communication.

Resources

- Efforts in WP2/4: TUA and KU Leuven.
- EU-Grant
- Knowledge from previous TNA services such as in RelReS.
- Experiences of TNA hosts and scholars.
- Communication channels of TNA Hosts.
- Ability to show the benefits of the RESILIENCE TNA programme to the stakeholders.
- Funding by UNISOFIA for one fellowship a year for a UNISOFIA scholar going abroad.
- annual TNA grant for KU Leuven, the accommodation grant for FSCIRE, and now also the ITSERR funded fellowships, until 31 October 2025.

3.4 Communication Strategy Frames for Other WUs

WU CDE has contacted the other WUs, discussing the question: how can communication support you in reaching your goals? This led to some concrete ideas, but it could be determined that no separate strategy (and thus no separate frame) needed to be developed for this, partly because of the regular personal contacts in this regard leading to regular content alongside the WP's developments.

3.5 Updated Set of KPIs

In close collaboration with the WU CDE TM, the partners working on TNA and working on communication/dissemination in Eastern Europe and the Balkans, an updated set of KPIs for the whole project period was realized. The set of KPIs can be found in the appendix.

Based on the reviewer's advice, an addition starting September 2024 has been made concerning Table 1, the RESILIENCE Key Performance Indicators for Awareness:

Target Audiences Reached in 2026:

- Academic: 200.000 people reached.
- Non-academic: 100.000 people reached via public media and RESILIENCE social media channels.
- New partners: 20 (TNA hosts, associate partners and observers).
- Decision makers: 3 forums at EuARe Annual conferences.
- Media: 50 publications in the media.

As to the newly added target audience of civil society, the KPIs are:

- 4 publications in traditional media (newspapers, magazines etc.), 25.000 people reached in total in this group.

3.6 Social Media Strategy

A social media strategy is included in the three communication strategy frames, since our news is not only disseminated through the website and newsletter, but also through our social media channels.

The Action Plan can be regarded as, and functions as a social media content calendar, since all relevant scheduled actions are expected to be shared on social media too.

The Action Plan also includes the planned data of deliverables, which gives the team the opportunity to generate news based on publications and share it via social media.

Strategic and operational use of the RESILIENCE social media channels can be found in the previously developed Guide for Social Media and Online Collaboration, accessible via the project repository.

During the period under review some additional actions have been developed:

- Starting M18, a series “Print Matters”, giving a platform to authors dealing with the topic of religion and its relevance, highlighting the physical aspect of our work and presenting academic works in the field of the study of religion on relevant topics with an innovative approach.
- A series “#voices”, asking people to reflect on questions related to our work building the research infrastructure.
- A website series “In our Service Catalogue” representing the existing services from Technology Readiness Level 7, as represented in Deliverable D2.2.
- To promote RelReSearch, the “One Click Away” series was developed with its own design in Adobe XD. It presents particularly interesting or outstanding examples of the online discovery environment RelReSearch. As the selection of the most suitable objects for social media and the creation of social media graphics is time-consuming, the series is produced at longer intervals.
- In addition, datasets from the RESILIENCE partners are presented that are of interest to our target group and which are available in open access.
- Use of the hashtag #resilienceatwork, for posting photos that show elements of our daily work.
- A planning for communication around TNA fellowships, included in the Action Plan.
- An idea for collaboration with the Italian project ITSERR was launched concerning a video series on services that are being developed during ITSERR’s project period.

3.7 Monitoring and Reporting

The monitoring and reporting systems have been significantly improved, leading to ease of use for all partners. The first improvement concerns working with one online form (the updated tracking file), which is the basis for all reports, where the format of the tracking file now matches as much as possible both RESILIENCE communication strategies and target audiences, as well as the information needed for ongoing reporting in the EC portal. Thus, partners only need to keep one form up to date, in which they report their actions and results.¹⁵ The second improvement concerns semi-automation of output, using Google Data Studio (also known as Looker Studio). TM can export by desired period, by partner, by channel, etc. This leads to a large number of overviews and charts, in this document you will find them for the period M1-M27

¹⁵ To support WU CDE members in this respect, a *Guide on Collecting Statistics* is available in the project repository.

in the Appendix. The connection between the tracking file and Google Data Studio was developed by RESILIENCE itself (WP2).

Semi-annual reporting has also begun, simultaneously with the semi-annual financial reporting provided by WP6, and in accordance with the agreements made during the kickoff meeting (whereby, by the way, the period from the previously agreed quarterly to semi-annual reporting was shifted, to avoid too much burden on the partners).

RESILIENCE Partner (use dropdown)	RESILIENCE Target Audiences Reached (use dropdown)	EC Target Audiences reached (use dropdown)	Communication Strategy Frame	Communication or Dissemination	Status of the Activity	How?
UNSA	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	General	Communication	Delivered	Other
UNSA	Decision Makers (Govern...	National authorities	General	Communication	Delivered	Other
UNI SOFIA	Media	Research Communities	General	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
UNI SOFIA	Decision Makers (Govern...	National authorities	Eastern Europe a	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
KUL	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
VOLOS	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	General	Communication	Delivered	Press Release
INFAI	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
INFAI	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
INFAI	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
INFAI	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
RESILIENCE WP4	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
RESILIENCE WP4	Academic (including me...	Research Communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
RESILIENCE WP4	New Partners (GLAM, po...	Specific user communities	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release
UNSA	Media	Citizens	TNA	Dissemination	Delivered	Press Release

Figure 6 Tracking Communications Statistics Online Sheet

4 From D4.1 to D4.2: Building Momentum

Following the key principles in Chapter 2 and the strategies presented in Chapter 3, we have been working on the implementation of our communication and dissemination activities. The statistics in the Appendix present concrete numbers that substantiate how we worked on our objectives and what the results are.

Simultaneously, we got to work with the focal points (4.1) and tasks (4.2) as described for our WP in the Grant Agreement,¹⁶ with advice from reviewers (4.3) and with our own directions for updating (4.4). From this, you can see that after two years, we are building momentum, because quite a number of tasks have been completed.

4.1 Focal Points

What	Work done	Result
1. The user's archetypes and a different strategy to reach out especially to scholars (with WP Users)	Contact WP2 in various months.	Knowledge that for the moment three archetypes were defined: librarians, archivists, scholars. ¹⁷ For the definition of our target groups, this means a refinement in the sense that the Libraries target group is now renamed and subdivided into Librarians and Archivists. This assumes that communication should not be further focused on the two subgroups of Librarians and Archivists, but that these target groups can be approached as one group. This refinement can be found in the Message House for Librarians/Archivists (fig.3). NB. The different strategy to reach out to scholars is in fact already in the matrices.
2. Refining the methodology to evaluate the impact of Communication & Dissemination Activities (with WP Impact)	Discussions with WP5 (UNSA).	Common agreement, that given the nature of impact (effect on the long term) it is not possible to evaluate it in the current phase. In D4.3, KPIs for the future should be established and the methodology (which is establishing and monitoring KPIs) should be described.
3. Tailoring the Communication & Dissemination Plan according to different religious /cultural/social contexts.	Internal discussions.	Tailoring to different religious and cultural contexts has been achieved by working with the geographic preconditions (D4.1, page 14/15), which are also incorporated into the various partner matrices (Appendix), combined with working with the Golden Circle model or Simon

¹⁶ GA 101079792, Description of the Action, Part A, 9.

¹⁷ Deliverable D3.3, 10. The archetypes are named: Dmitris (archivist), Dunja (librarian), Francesco (PhD), Maja (University Professor).

		Sinek (par. 2.7). Adaptation to different social contexts is not (yet) on the agenda due to the lack of a concrete service catalog.
4. Understanding the terms of an exploitation strategy for the RI.	Study of the topic by TUA, discussion with WU CDE TM.	Updated Chapter 7 in D4.2
5. Addressing the issue of KPIs for the specific RESILIENCE RI: typology and measurement methodology.	Internal discussions, study on the subject, asking advice from EHRI RI.	Solved, except for impact KPIs, planned November 2024, and stakeholder KPIs. See Appendix for updated KPIs.
6. Improving the public representation and public image of the RI.	Internal discussions.	The public representation is constantly under review and update. At the moment we see no need to improve the public image.
7. Ensuring a more effective connection to civil society and the private sector.	Internal discussion, consulting other communication/dissemination plans.	Conclusion: ensuring a more effective connection is not possible in this phase. However, we can include civil society to our target audiences, generic partner matrix and KPIs, which we did (reaching civil society via traditional media and social media). The private sector comes into the picture as soon as steps are taken toward exploitation. This could include bringing in publishing houses.
8. Taking into consideration the specific needs of different academic communities in dissemination actions.	Internal discussion. Checking needs with WWU.	See generic matrix describing the different academic communities (professors, Phd's etc.).
9. Working on a more defined communication about how RESILIENCE contributes to the skills of its users.	Internal discussion.	Updated set of general messages (par 2.5). Discussing with the Italian project ITSERR the idea of a video series communicating the value of ITSERR services for the RI users.

Table 3 Work Done and Results Focal Points

4.2 Tasks

What	Work done	Result
10. Work on internal communication related to the views within the consortium about the RI itself and specific services like ReReSearch before putting in place a PULL approach.	Work on updated vision/mission statement Discuss services with WP2	New vision/mission statement, dated January 2024. Moderate expectation regarding services until the service catalog is ready.
11. Discuss the recommendation of the ESFRI reviewers December 2021 and try to incorporate them in the upcoming version of D5.3 (2022): Take into consideration the specific needs of different academic communities in future dissemination actions for the RESILIENCE infrastructure (Recommendation 11 of the current CDP).	Internal discussion, alignment with the work of WP users.	See point 8 of par. 4.1 of D4.2.
12. Discuss recommendations 1-10 ¹⁸ as described in the current CDP and take measures that will secure inclusion in the updated version(s) of the CDP. Recommendation 1 Develop a Strategy to Connect with Other European Projects and RIs for the Preparatory Phase. Recommendation 2 Formulate a brand promise for the various target audiences, including the <i>roots</i> of the brand and the <i>wings</i> of the brand. <i>Roots</i> are the functional mark promise and <i>brands</i> the emotional mark promise. For example: "RESILIENCE makes the newest tools and instruments available, so that you can become the best scholar (cf. Van Liemt/Koot, 231).	Internal discussion. Internal communication training M11, further discussion.	Agile approach: intensify existing contacts (see footnote 5), enter into new contacts based on a desire for exchange, advice or cooperation, appoint experts in this field in RESILIENCE's Advisory Board. This recommendation is obsolete, as it was decided in M9 to work with the Golden Circle instead, see par. 2.7

¹⁸ Recommendation 1-10 from D5.3 RESILIENCE Design Phase incorporated into D4.1 RESILIENCE PPP. D4.1 left 6 recommendations.

<p>Recommendation 3 Check with the target audiences if the brand promise is relevant, distinctive and credible. Regarding the Push and Pull approach (see par. 3.2.2) RESILIENCE is focusing on strengthening the Pull effect of its approach. To that aim, the feedback of the partners will be used.</p> <p>Recommendation 4 Organize a brainstorming meeting with RESILIENCE partners about their experiences with Pull related actions (like presence in the media and attending workshops and conferences) and discuss best practices. Implement these best practices in the updated version(s) of the CDP. Discuss also the content of the communication and dissemination activities: how can we better show the added value of RESILIENCE, so that target audiences will act as leaders instead of targets?</p> <p>Recommendation 5 Stay in close contact with service developers. Once a basic version or even full version [of the service catalogue] is available, actively engage in communications to reach the targeted audiences.</p> <p>Recommendation 6 Discuss the recommendation of the ESFRI reviewers December 2021 and try to incorporate them in D4.2: take into consideration the specific needs of different academic communities in future dissemination actions for the RESILIENCE infrastructure.</p>	<p>Internal communication training M11, further discussion.</p> <p>Planned M30.</p> <p>A helpful means is the updated Vision/ Mission statement, mentioning the values.</p> <p>Ongoing</p> <p>See task 11.</p>	<p>This recommendation is obsolete, as it was decided in M9 to work with the Golden Circle instead, see par. 2.7. However, a sample test with 3 people from each target audience to see if the brand promise is relevant is planned in M40.</p> <p>Service catalog is expected in M30.</p> <p>Completed</p>
<p>13. Discuss the evaluation of the EC reviewers December 2023 as described in the paragraph on the criterion impact, and take measures that will secure inclusion in the updated version(s) of the CDP.</p>	<p>Final review report and impact session was discussed internally.</p>	<p>See task 2.</p>

<p>14. Define the differentiated strategy to reach out to the RESILIENCE users archetypes and especially to scholars</p>	<p>Discussed with the WP3 team if archetypes fit into the target groups.</p>	<p>Completed, see 4.1 point 1.</p>
<p>15. Consult with institutions that already developed best practises in the field of communicating religious related topics (e.g. curators of religious heritage).</p>	<p>Contacts with the Dutch ministry of OCW, church/religious heritage insurance company, publisher, Prisma and local municipality.</p>	<p><i>Best practice 1:</i> Schnell und Steiner Kirchenführer (church guides): communicate regularly in newsletters, make the guides cheap and handy and make them available on site: seeing is buying. <i>Best practice 2:</i> Prisma Association, Netherlands. Methodology to engage in open and equal conversation, ensuring mutual respect and avoiding prejudice or misconceptions: LAST PRISMA DOC and Full article: A Bridge Over Troubled Water: How Worldview Helps Overcome the Religious-Secular Divide in Development Cooperation and Beyond. No reaction from the local municipality.</p>
<p>16. Exploit the network of the RelReS TNA grantholders to gain insights on how to (better) communicate the results of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme</p>	<p>Online meeting with RelReS TNA grant-holders in M5.</p>	<p>Improved TNA communication workflow and input for Communication Strategy Frame TNA 01.00 (in D4.1).</p>
<p>17. Organise face to face meetings in collaboration with the WP USERS with selected target audiences in order to get a deeper insight into their needs and how to improve their skills, as well as their image of the RI.</p>	<p>(Support in) organisation of User Needs Workshop in Sofia (M9), Ljubljana (M10), Volos (M12) and Münster (M17).</p>	<p>Deeper insights were incorporated in WP2's deliverables, on which WP4 can adjust its communication strategy in due course. The expectations of the RI seen from the side of meeting participants have been evaluated. Results can be found in chapter 6.3 of this document. Other information concerning the needs and how to improve skills has been passed on to WP users. Some examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By providing library resources and creating possibilities of European-wide scholarly networking. • possibility for mobility • Events for sensibilisation of the decision makers and the society about specificity of the research in Humanities. • Affordability and effectiveness of a future platform. • A platform specifically for connecting with other researchers in similar fields to allow for discussion, acquaintance and exchange of views on common research issues will be particularly important and helpful.
<p>18. Update and implement the RESILIENCE C&D Plan, facilitate, stimulate and monitor the activities planned</p>	<p>Ongoing</p>	<p>After setting up a semi-automated reporting system, six-monthly monitoring of activities began from M13, resulting in internal reports.</p>

<p>19. Define roles and responsibilities of the participating partners and other partners willing to contribute to the implementation</p>	<p>Ongoing</p>	<p>In general partners agree to the responsibilities in this plan (being multipliers and initiators in the cycle of communication, distributing RESILIENCE news, especially the press releases in a certain geographical context, and finally reporting their activities. Besides, the agile approach was adopted, meaning that partners, having efforts, experience, capabilities and willingness to contribute in kind, may switch from roles during the PPP as long as they use their efforts and keep the agreements. Agreements have been made jointly on the distribution of news, presentations, etc. as presented in the Action Plan, where the line between in-kind and work for efforts is not always clear.</p>
<p>20. Propose a strategy for the exploitation of RESILIENCE results.</p>	<p>Study of the topic by TUA.</p>	<p>Updated Chapter 7 in D4.2</p>
<p>21. Develop new or updated communication means like flyers, banners etc.</p>	<p>Comparing means with project developments, ongoing activity</p>	<p>New versions of roll-up banner, service card fellowships, new QR-code card, new two sided RESILIENCE/ EuARe A6 card, A4 folded flyer with vision/mission statement, format for social media images using Adobe XD, videos for the YouTube channel.</p>
<p>22. Elaborate a green approach to communication meetings, ensuring alternatives to physical meetings</p>	<p>Internal alignment.</p>	<p>Completed: Page 113, 114, 115 of D4.1</p>
<p>23. Support WP SUSTAINABILITY in all communication activities aiming at the establishment of the ERIC and alignment of national strategies, and adopt a dedicated communication strategy aiming at establishing new partnerships with academic and non-academic data holders</p>	<p>First part is a constant offer, WP1 is aware of this. As to the second part, this task has been allocated to the Enlargement Committee. WP4 supports the committee as much as possible.</p>	<p>Completed: at the time of writing this deliverable 7 institutions joined RESILIENCE as an associated partner or as an observer. WP4 also provides support to the growing cooperation with ITSERR (the Italian project designed to strengthen the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE according to the needs of the Religious Studies scientific community), for example around communication about the five TNA Hosts from the ITSERR consortium.</p>

Table 4 Work done and Results Tasks

4.3 Advice Reviewers 04/10/2023

What	Work done	Result
24. Work with living documents and keep better track of progress.	Included in Action plan: check Action Plan quarterly and ask partners for updates. Update of Status in Action Plan: Delivered/Canceled/Ongoing/Postponed.	Ongoing
25. Make KPIs more quantifiable	Update of KPIs for the whole project period in alignment with the developments so far. Decision to prepare a 6-month report of key results. update the monitoring/reporting system supported by Google Data Studio.	Updated KPIs completed. Delivery of M13-M18 report in M24. Delivery of M19-M24 report in M25. Monthly overview of KPI results for the three frames in an online KPI overview.
26. Avoid pushing forward writing the Impact and Exploitation chapters in the Communication/Dissemination/Exploitation plan	Decision to include first versions in D4.2 and final versions in D4.3. Study of the topic, alignment with the CDE Team.	In progress. To be finalized in D4.3.
27. Report EC based on review October 2023 inviting the team to define more quantifiable and measurable KPIs for each of the stakeholders	Internal discussion.	An addition to the KPI overview related to the target audiences was made: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academics: 200.00. • Non-academic: 100.000 people reached via public media and RESILIENCE social media channels. • New partners: 20 (TNA hosts, associate partners and observers). • Decision makers: 3 forums at EuARe Annual conferences. • Media: 50 publications in the media.
28. RESILIENCE could more efficiently develop the digital tools and online advertising, yet the social media and digital dissemination are at this time not yet developed as much as they could.	Discussed within the WU CDE Team.	For better findability of RelReSearch, in M19 the domain reiresearch was also purchased, which links to reiresearch.eu. Increased use of videos/reels on social media. Discussing with the Italian project ITSERR the idea of a video series communicating the value of ITSERR services for the RI users.

Table 5 Work done and Results Advice Reviewer

4.4 RESILIENCE Updates

The following updates have been made according to project developments and insights gained recently:

What	Work done	Result
29. Refine the academic target audience, like towards disciplines.	Discussed in M25; given the progress in the project there seems to be no need for further refinement towards the different disciplines.	If needed, TM can adapt messages themselves towards different contexts making use of the Golden Circle of Sinek as practiced during a workshop M11, see par.2.7 of this document
30. Update press contact list beyond humanities October 2023 (based on review meeting 03.10.2023).	Collection of email addresses, added to press contact list.	Extended press contact list with contacts of law/economics/legal history/.
30. Inspiration by the Common Compass.	Corresponding to the extent to which the compass is evident internally in communication, a small video series for online distribution was made.	5 explainer videos on YouTube.

Table 6 Work done and Results RESILIENCE updates

5 Action Plan M13-27

The actions scheduled for M13-M27 as listed in the online Action Plan can be found in the appendix.

6 Main Results and Achievements

6.1 KPIs and Results M1-M27

See Attachment 1 in the Appendix.

6.2 Overviews Results M1-M27

See Attachment 1 in the Appendix.

6.3 Event Evaluation M1-M27

6.3.1 General

RESILIENCE hosted a number of events, both online and offline. Where possible, an online evaluation form was offered via Google forms.¹⁹ The results of the evaluations are shown in the table below. Beginning with M6, the evaluations are offered in a more equally structured form, so that material becomes comparable.

¹⁹ Offering an online evaluation form is not always possible, e.g. on conferences where a panel was held without people having to register.

Nr.	Description	M	Nr. of participants	Nr. of respondents	Type of audience (internal/external) ²⁰	General Goal Achievement ²¹	Score	Overall impression ²²
1	RESILIENCE meets researchers in Bulgaria	9	17	4	Internal/external	Evaluated in another form		Not evaluated
2	Communication training	9	10	10	Internal	Evaluated in another form		Not evaluated
3	Webinar Albania	10	20	11	External	Very good		Not evaluated
4	Workshop Chatgod (KUL)	11	40	6	External	Good		Not evaluated
5	RESILIENCE meets researchers in Greece	12	15	8	External	Evaluated in another form		Not evaluated
6	Webinar TUA	13	10	4	External	Good		8,0
7	FAIR Data Online Workshop	15	22	7	Internal/external	Good		8,3
8	Interview Training Münster	17	11	7	Internal/external	Good		8,6
9	Workshop Münster	17	11	6	External	Good		7,8
10	Online Demo RelReSearch	19	22	10	External	Good		8,2
11	Training Workshop Leipzig	22	13	13	Internal	Good		8,5
12	RESILIENCE Meets Researchers in Sarajevo	12	8	5	External	Very Good		9
13	Training Prototype "Software TRACER – Text Reuse Detection Machine"	29	15	10	Internal	Very good		9,1
14	Data Management Training for RESILIENCE and ITSERR	29	22	8	Internal + ITSERR	Not applicable		9,3

Table 7 Event Evaluation M1-M27

As the above overview shows, and based on the interviews received (which are not necessarily representative), the tentative conclusion can be drawn that, in general, participants felt that the goals were well addressed. The overall rating is also high. Some degree of social desirability may be to blame for this; this has not been checked. On the other hand, criticisms and recommendations were also shared, which were then shared within the consortium with a view to using that feedback for organizing future events.

²⁰ Internal means: affiliated with a RESILIENCE partner, not necessarily belonging to the core-team.

²¹ Rating: Poor, Satisfactory, Good, Very Good.

²² Rating on a range from 1-10, whereby 10 is the highest score.

The event evaluation reports are shared widely within the consortium so that future event organizers can benefit from them.

6.3.2 Communication Goals

Evaluations 1, 5, 6, 9, and 12 also asked about the extent to which two communication goals were met, see figures 7 and 8.²³

The completed evaluation forms show the following results:²⁴

Figure 7 Evaluation of communication goal 1: "I have gained a clear insight into RESILIENCE"

²³ In the situation where the two communication goals were not checked, this had to do with the nature of the event. In an event in which only people involved in RESILIENCE participated, evaluating these goals was not necessary. Other events did not lend themselves very well, if at all, to evaluating the communication goals because a concrete presentation/exchange about them was lacking.

²⁴ Representativeness was not considered.

Figure 8 Evaluation of communication goal 2: "I am convinced of the necessity of a European Research Infrastructure for the study of religion."

Regarding the average impression of the participant as expressed on a scale of 1-10, a trend towards increasing appreciation can be observed (from 8,0 to 9,3). However, it must be remembered that not all events had the same audience (external/internal/mixed), so a comparison here is probably incomplete.

As to the evaluation of the communication goals, the score indicates that the goals have been more than convincingly reached.

7 Exploitation Strategy: Elements and Steps

7.1 Introduction²⁵

The European Commission defines exploitation as

- the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned,
- or in developing, creating, and marketing a product or process,
- or in creating and providing a service,
- or in standardisation activities.

Exploitation can be commercial, societal, political, or for improving public knowledge and action.

The Grant Agreement defines in relation to exploitation the objective to understand “the terms of an exploitation strategy for the RI” as well as “propose a strategy for the exploitation of RESILIENCE results”.²⁶

Below both objectives have been combined, which means that the elements which an exploitation strategy for RESILIENCE should contain – this is how ‘terms’ is understood - are listed, as well as a proposal for strategic steps to be taken to ensure successful exploitation in the implementation phase. The assumption here is that RESILIENCE’s results only come to exploitation in the phases following the preparatory phase, starting with the implementation phase (from 2026 onwards).

7.2 Elements of an Exploitation Strategy

RESILIENCE’s Exploitation Strategy involves the following elements

- Description of the main objectives of the exploitation.
- Description of methods for exploitation.
- Description of strategic steps towards exploitation.

²⁵ Main Sources used: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/events/2017-03-01/8_result-dissemination-exploitation.pdf (retrieved July 2024)
https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/dissemination-and-exploitation-research-results_en (retrieved July 2024).
Video *Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation in Horizon Europe* <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gyXIYDkXQ2E> (retrieved July 2024).

²⁶ Grant Agreement 101079792, Part A, 9 and 10.

7.3 Exploitation Objectives

- Maximize the impact of RESILIENCE.
- Utilisation of RESILIENCE's exploitable results.

7.4 Methods

- Identification of target groups.
- Mapping of exploitable results.
- Establishing and maintaining mechanisms for effective exploitation of the project results
- Identifying barriers to effective exploitation and to effective exploitation activities.
- Spreading, as effectively as possible, RESILIENCE's exploitable results among target groups on a timely basis.
- Exploring options for cooperation.

7.5 Strategic Steps Towards the Exploitation of Results

Exploitation can only start once the research results and services are available, but an initial strategy for exploitation can be formulated on the basis of the expected results. This implies the need to reckon with unexpected exploitable results.

Exploitation focuses on the actual use of the results, translating the products of RESILIENCE (research results, services, etc.) into concrete solutions that have a positive impact on the public's quality of life, on the market, on further research development.

The project results are both tangible and intangible. Tangible results could include practical tools or products; intangible results may include skills and personal experiences gained by the project participants, as well as the knowledge they gain from participation.

This leads to ten strategic steps towards the exploitation of results:

1. **Set up** an exploitation plan describing the tangible and intangible results of the project and defining its best exploitation.
2. **Ensure** that appropriate intellectual property rights (IPR) strategies are considered and applied, for the optimal exploitation of project results.
3. **Create** visibility of project results among target audiences, raise general awareness to promote use of project results.
4. **Disseminate** results towards the various target groups through organization of, and participation at conferences or fairs; face to face meetings with selected target audiences; webinars, preferably with

hands-on sessions; online training sessions; social media, contests and awards etc. and other touchpoints.

5. **Communicate** results and their possible use and relevance towards decision/policy makers, citizens, religious communities and funding organizations.
6. **Offer** marketable results to publishing companies and other data collectors.
7. **Start** towards the scientific community and institutions a “How to join the Research Infrastructure” campaign.
8. **Prepare** models of transactions between stakeholders (e.g. companies, public actors) and the RI (e.g. supporting the development of services; acquiring knowledge and/or software; accessing the platform).
9. **Perform** a risk analysis related to the exploitation of results.
10. **Describe** terms to safeguard the availability, quality, and maintenance of the results after the project’s funding lifecycle.

8 Conclusions and Actions to Take

8.1 Conclusions

8.1.1 General

RESILIENCE PPP is building momentum and on its way to achieving its goals and handling various tasks. What has not been completed yet (or not enough) will be described in the last version of the plan, Deliverable D4.3.

The work has benefited from the previously chosen principles and methods: the agile approach and the communication strategy frames. These choices allow the consortium to be flexible, to adapt as needed and to present strategies in an orderly fashion so that the TM can always quickly see what the starting points for the communication and dissemination are.

8.1.2 M1-M27 Statistics

Awareness and Engagement

In terms of awareness, results are moving in the right direction. With the exception perhaps of the number of newsletter subscribers, it looks like the KPIs will be met. On the other hand, the newsletters are well read by subscribers, the numbers for open rate and click rate are much higher than the average numbers on which the KPIs are based. In particular, the website statistics show a favorable picture: the website was visited more often, longer and by more people than expected. When it comes to engagement, the results are also good, although engagement on Facebook could be better.

Communication Strategy Frame TNA

The numbers for TNA are definitely satisfactory, which no doubt has to do with the calls for applications for Transnational Access Fellowships that were launched during the reporting period.

Communication Strategy Frame Eastern Europe and the Balkans

Partners also achieved good results in Eastern Europe and the Balkans: more than 100000 people could be reached with news of RESILIENCE. In parts, however, the results seem to lag behind the KPIs set for the PPP phase, whereas it is possible that data may be missing. Partners are active in general, but may overlook reporting all their activities. Extra attention is needed here.

Target Audiences Reached

As for the total target groups reached as further specified in Chapter 3, it appears that we can achieve good results by leveraging the strengths of our partners. For example, some partners reach large platforms,

others are able to reach media or have a large reach of their newsletters. Together we arrive at a good score. With social media, we reach most of our target audiences. As to the different types of target audiences, we do reach our own target audiences and part of the EU target audiences. Regarding the latter, more attention to civil society resp. citizens will be paid. Some new KPIs have been included for that.

Strengths of Partners

As for the total target groups reached as further specified in Chapter 3, it appears that we can achieve good results by leveraging the strengths of our partners. For example, some partners reach large platforms, others are able to reach media or have extensive reach with their newsletters. Together we arrive at a good score. With social media, we reach most of our target audiences. As to the different types of target audiences, we do reach our own target audiences and part of the EU target audiences. Regarding the latter, more attention to civil society and citizens will be paid. Some new KPIs have been included for that.

Other

For outcome, 1 KPI was established: an average of 50 registrations per event. However, the outcome until now (average of 17 registrations per event) is lagging. This may be because of the number of RESILIENCE events so far, or perhaps because we were a bit too optimistic here.

Work has to be done on establishing impact KPIs.

Website

The website statistics are very satisfactory. The website has been visited more often, longer and by more people, especially around the launch of the calls for applications for TNA. Besides interest in the concrete offerings, people are also interested in the profile of RESILIENCE: what does this RI stand for?

Social Media

In general, the results of social media activities have been good. This is certainly due to the activity of all involved in the network, and especially those from Eastern Europe and The Balkans. As they are quite active on social media, liking and sharing posts, reach is increasing considerably. However, more input could be collected for social media, e.g., where it comes to TNA, working sessions (#resilienceatwork) and presentations by partners at various events. Results of other WPs' work, as well as more differentiated results of WP2, could also be highlighted more. It is expected that the latter will become more concrete during the coming period and can therefore be communicated more widely.

8.2 Actions to Take

1. Discuss with WU CDE TM how to increase Facebook engagement.
2. Discuss KPIs and the results of Communication Strategy Frame Eastern Europe and the Balkans with partners in the region, to see further work with the KPIs.
3. Schedule meeting(s) with UNSA to define impact KPIs for communication/dissemination.
4. Develop a strategy/make a plan for reaching civil society in the coming years.
5. Check bi-annually focal points (4.1), tasks (4.2), advice from reviewers (4.3), and our own directions for updating (4.4) to see how to work on it further, as needed.
6. Pay increased attention to the possibility of newsletter subscriptions.

Appendix

This Appendix contains a number of attachments, not part of the public deliverable.

- Attachment 1: Report WP₄ Statistics M₁-M₂₇
- Attachment 2: Action Plan M₁₃-M₂₇
- Attachment 3: Partner Matrices

Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
A1	28/08/2022	Grant Agreement 101079792
A2	Various	Various Guides in the G-Drive WU CDE repository
A3	18/11/2022	Deliverable D4.1

Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	September 2020	RESILIENCE ex ante Socio-Economic Impact Study, n.d., Attachment 3.7 to ESFRI Roadmap questionnaire
R2	September 2020	RESILIENCE First Progress Report (02/09/2019 – 01/09/2020, 14/09/2020)
R3	December 2021	European Commission Review Report
R4	September 2022	Governance set up proceedings, D6.1
R5	November 2022	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan D4.1
R6	December 2023	European Commission Review Report

Revision Log

ID	Date	Nature of Revision	Approved by
R1	M26-M30	Working version, collecting input from WP TM	WP leader
R2	M30	Editorial review, minor textual adaptations	WP leader
R3	M30	Internal review	

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